

Geographical notes on Iberian Caudofoveata (Mollusca)

Notas geográficas sobre los Caudofoveata (Mollusca) ibéricos

Luitfried v. SALVINI-PLAWEN*

Recibido el 29-IV-2009. Aceptado el 2-X-2009

ABSTRACT

New records of Caudofoveata from samplings off Barcelona and off Galicia are presented. They concern *Chaetoderma*(?) *strigisquamatum* transferred to *Falcidens* and *F. vasconiensis* as well as two other species of *Falcidens* and two of *Prochaetoderma* s.l. This represents a noteworthy enlargement of the known geographical distribution. Some organisational characters of the species are added.

RESUMEN

Se presentan nuevas citas de Caudofoveata procedentes de las costas de Barcelona y Galicia: *Chaetoderma*(?) *strigisquamatum* transferido en *Falcidens* y *F. vasconiensis*, así como otras dos especies de *Falcidens* y dos de *Prochaetoderma* s.l. Se amplía el conocimiento de su distribución geográfica y se añaden algunos caracteres en la organización de las especies.

INTRODUCTION

Caudofoveata are worm-shaped molluscs of generally 2-30 mm but up to 40 cm in length that burrow in marine sediments in depths of 50-9000 m, under special conditions as shallow as 3 m. They are externally characterised by an aplousophoran mantle with chitinous cuticle as well as unicellularly produced aragonitic sclerites; together with the Solenogastres, both clades reflect conservative levels of molluscan configuration (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003, 2006). Currently, 125 species of Caudofoveata are described. Our knowledge of the diversity and distribution of the species in Iberian waters is still poor (cf. SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1997). Apart from five taxa belonging to the bathial deep sea fauna of the eastern Atlantic, the known representatives of the Iberian shelf region include nine Caudofoveata species (cf.

SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1997; SCHELTEMA AND IVANOV, 2000). Material from more recent samplings revealed an enlargement of the geographical distribution of six species belonging to the Chaetodermatidae and Prochaetodermatidae.

MATERIAL EXAMINED

Caudofoveata were present in several samples from off Barcelona collected during the BIOMARE project (CTM2006-13508-C02-02) from the continental slope and canyon at 41° 03' - 41° 15' N, 02° 04' - 02° 28' E, 550-850 m (see Table I). This material was provided by Joan Cartes and Valeria Mamouridis from the Institut de Ciències del Mar (CMIMA-CSIC) in Barcelona.

*Zentrum für organismische Systembiologie: Zoologie, Universität Wien, Althanstraße 14, A-1090 WIEN, Austria; Luitfried.Salvini-Plawen@univie.ac.at

Table I. BIOMARE project and DIVA-Artabia sampling stations.

Tabla I. Estaciones de muestreo de los proyectos BIOMARE y DIVA-Artabia.

BIOMARE station	coordinates	depth	species
BIOM 1, BC 8 (27.02.07) (c. slope)	41°09'55"N, 02°25'59"E	850 m	<i>P. alleni</i>
BIOM 1, BC 10 (27.02.07) (c. slope)	41°09'55"N, 02°25'59"E	800 m	<i>F. strigisquamatus</i>
BIOM 2, BC 7 (april 2007) (c. slope)	41°10'00"N, 02°28'03"E	800 m	<i>F. strigisquamatus</i>
BIOM 2, BC 11 (april 2007) (canyon)	41°14'36"N, 02°26'58"E	600 m	<i>F. gutturosus</i>
BIOM 3, BC 3 (july 2007) (canyon)	41°14'36"N, 02°28'49"E	650 m	<i>F. gutturosus, F. aequabilis</i>
BIOM 3, BC 8 (july 2007) (c. slope)	41°10'01"N, 02°26'25"E	800 m	<i>P. alleni</i>
BIOM 3, BC 14 (july 2007) (canyon)	41°03'52"N, 02°11'29"E	800 m	<i>F. strigisquamatus</i>
BIOM 3, BC 18 (july 2007) (canyon)	41°08'11"N, 02°04'37"E	650 m	<i>F. strigisquamatus</i>
BIOM 4, BC 3 (4.10.07) (canyon)	41°14'48"N, 02°26'28"E	650 m	<i>P. boucheti, P. alleni</i>
BIOM 4, BC 4 (4.10.07) (canyon)	41°14'48"N, 02°26'28"E	650 m	<i>P. alleni, F. aequabilis</i>
BIOM 8, BC 6 (feb. 2008) (canyon)	41°14'57"N, 02°27'00"E	550 m	<i>F. strigisquamatus</i>
DIVA-Artabia projects			
EBS-150 m (14.09.03)	43°33'N, 08°35'W		<i>P. boucheti</i>
EBS-162 m (03.07.06)	43°34'N, 08°36'30"W		<i>P. boucheti</i>
EBS-200 m (11.09.03)	43°40'N, 08°43'W		<i>P. boucheti</i>
EBS-250 m (14.09.02)	43°41'30"N, 08°45'W		<i>F. vasconiensis, P. boucheti</i>
EBS-300 m (13.09.02)	43°42'N, 08°46'W		<i>P. boucheti</i>
EBS-300 m (19.09.03)	43°42'N, 08°46'W		<i>F. vasconiensis</i>
EBS-400 m (13.09.02)	43°44'N, 08°48'W		<i>F. vasconiensis, P. boucheti</i>

Samples with Caudofoveata were also available from the DIVA-Artabia projects (PGIDT01PXI20008PE; CTM-2004-00740/MAR; PGIDT07PXIB000120PR) organised by Victoriano Urgorri (University of Santiago de Compostela) and conducted off NW-Galicia in the Gulf of Ártabro outside the Ria de Ferrol between 43° 28' N, 08° 28' W and 45° 43' N, 09° 00' W, at 100-1000

m depth; the samples were taken in September 2002, September 2003 and July 2006 using an epibenthic sledge (EBS) (Table I).

The holotype of *Chaetoderma(?) strigisquamatum* Salvini-Plawen (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle Paris no. 21094) has been re-examined with respect to the mantle sclerites.

RESULTS

Family CHAETODERMATIDAE

Falcidens strigisquamatus (Salvini-Plawen, 1977)

Chaetoderma(?) strigisquamatum Salvini-Plawen, 1977. *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Nat. Paris* 3^e sér. (447), Zool 310: 419

[Type locality: Western Mediterranean Sea, Alborán Basin; 1491 m]

This species was known based on a single specimen from the Sea of Alborán and tentatively described under the genus *Chaetoderma(?)* (SALVINI-PLAWEN,

1977a). The investigations from off Barcelona yielded five additional individuals at 550-800 m (a voucher specimen is deposited in the Museo Nacional

Figures 1-4. *Falcidens strigisquamatus*. 1: mantle sclerites, a-b from the foregut region, c-e from the midgut region, f-h from the region of the midgut sac, h from the prepallial region, i-j from the pallial region, k from alongside the dorsoterminal sense organ; 2: mantle sclerite (60 x 20 µm) from the anterior foregut region of the holotype (see Figure 1a); 3: mantle sclerites from the anterior foregut region of specimen BIOM 3, BC 4; sclerite at left = 60 x 19 µm (see Figure 1a); 4: name-giving mantle scales from the regions of the midgut and midgut sac of specimen BIOM 3, BC 4 (see Figure 1e-g).

Figuras 1-4. Falcidens strigisquamatus. 1: escleritos del manto, a-b de la región anterior del tubo digestivo, c-e de la región media del tubo digestivo, f-h de la región del saco digestivo, h de la región prepaleal, i-j de la región paleal, k de la zona del órgano sensorial dorsoterminal; 2: escleritos del manto (60 x 20 µm) de la región anterior del tubo digestivo del holotipo (ver Figura 1a); 3: escleritos del manto de la región anterior del tubo digestivo del espécimen BIOM 3, BC 4, esclerito de la izquierda 60 x 19 µm (ver Figura 1a); 4: escamas del manto, mostrando el dibujo que da nombre a la especie, de las regiones media del tubo digestivo y del saco digestivo, del espécimen BIOM 3, BC 4 (ver Figura 1e-g).

de Ciencias Naturales MNCN, Madrid, no. 15.01/0005): BIOM 1, BC 10 (1 ind., 8 mm); BIOM 2, BC 7 (1 ind., broken, anteriormost body region missing, 8.5 mm); BIOM 3, BC 14 (1 ind., 22 mm); BIOM 3,

BC 18 (1 ind., 19 mm) (voucher specimen in MNCN); BIOM 8, BC 6 (1 ind., anteriormost body region missing, 15.5 mm)

Beyond the biogeographical data, some organisational features are added

here to supplement the original description (holotype re-examined in Sept. 2008): (1) The species reaches a body length of 22 mm and occasionally the posteriormost region (of the pallial cavity) shows some orange incrustation. (2) The sclerites of the mantle cover (Fig. 1) at the middle and posterior body (region of midgut sac, "posterior trunk") are 140-350 μm long and of the special type to which the name is alluding. These elongate scales have longitudinal ridges and furrows of different number and length (Salvini-Plawen, 1977a; Figs 1 f-h and 4) and sometimes are slightly asymmetrical. The scales of the midgut region ("anterior trunk"; Fig. 1 c-e) are almost radially arranged. The sclerites of the anterior body (foregut region, "neck") show some variation correlated to the size (age) of the specimens: Large individuals possess a characteristic type of small, slender scales ranging from 30 x 12 μm to 70 x 25 μm and 75 x 18 μm (Figs 1 a, 2, 3), which in

smaller animals of up to 9 mm in length (re-examined holotype and other) are only sporadically present. In contrast, smaller specimens possess in the anterior body region roughly triangular scales (Fig. 1 b), which are scarce in large animals. (3) The pedal shield (about 300 x 200 μm) is preorally fused by a not very prominent narrow portion (Fig. 6). (3) The frontally bilobed cerebral ganglion has a distinct lobus impar. (4) The radula, scarcely visible in transparent whole mounts (see holotype), is represented by a pair of sickle-shaped teeth as is characteristic for the genus *Falcidens* (Salvini-Plawen 1968); the teeth are about 45 μm long and no symphysis could be discerned. In the largest specimen, the whole apparatus (Fig. 5) showed an un-reinforced basal cone only 105 μm long (50 μm wide, 20 μm thick), the two short lateral supports (55 μm long, 50 μm wide) and small muscular radula bolsters ("odontophores"; 80 x \varnothing 50 μm).

Falcidens vasconiensis Salvini-Plawen, 1996

Falcidens vasconiensis Salvini-Plawen, 1996. *Bull. Soc. Zool. France* 121: 341.
[Type locality: East Atlantic, SE Bay of Biscay, Cap Breton; 141-170 m]

The species had been described from the southeastern-most region of the Bay of Biscaya (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1996, 1999). The new records with three individuals at 250 m (4.5 mm), 300 m (5.5 mm) and 400 m (3 mm) evidence the presence of the species also off NW-Galicia.

The mantle sclerites of the present specimens show some individual variation but are typical for *F. vasconiensis*

(Fig. 3 in SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1999). The radula apparatus of the smallest specimen (3 mm) with two pairs of lateral supports confirms the conspecificity (cf. Fig. 4 in SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1999); only the pair of sickle-shaped teeth (pincers; 45 μm long) and the distal portion of the basal cone are reinforced. The pedal shield (about 150 x 135 μm) laterally flanks the mouth opening (Fig. 6).

Family PROCHAETODERMAIDAE

Prochaetoderma boucheti Scheltema and Ivanov, 2000

Prochaetoderma boucheti Scheltema and Ivanov, 2000. *Journ. Moll. Stud.* 66: 336
[Type locality: Western Mediterranean Sea, off Ceuta (Morocco); 425 m]

This species had been partly confused with the sympatric *P. iberogallicum* Salvini-Plawen, 1999, from which it

differs by two rows of pedal shield scales and by the (likewise short, up to 135 μm) elongate midbody sclerites pro-

Figure 5. *Falcidens strigisquamatus*, hard parts of the radula apparatus; basal cone outlined in natural position and when turned into the plane (dashed line). Figure 6. Pedal shields of *Falcidens strigisquamatus* (above) and *Falcidens vasconiensis* (below).

Figura 5. *Falcidens strigisquamatus*, partes duras del aparato radular; barra basal dibujada en su posición natural y doblada sobre el plano (línea discontinua). Figura 6. Escudos pedios de *Falcidens strigisquamatus* (arriba) y *Falcidens vasconiensis* (abajo).

vided with a distal median keel (SCHELTEMA AND IVANOV, 2001). In some regions it is also sympatric with *P. alleni* (below): Apart from the published Iberian distribution of *P. boucheti* from the southern Bay of Biscay, the Gulf of Cádiz, from off Ceuta and from off Málaga (SCHELTEMA AND IVANOV, 2000,

2001), additional findings can be reported.

There are several records of *P. boucheti* from Galicia outside the Ria de Ferrol at 150-400 m, predominantly at 150 m. In addition, a single specimen was found off Barcelona with BIOM 4, BC 3 (650 m).

Prochaetoderma alleni (Scheltema and Ivanov, 2000)

Spathoderma alleni Scheltema and Ivanov, 2000. *Journ. Moll. Stud.* 66: 358
[Type locality: East Atlantic, Bay of Biscay; 860 m]

The species is known from Iceland to the Mediterranean (IVANOV AND SCHELTEMA, 2001) and in some regions it is sympatric with *P. boucheti* (above); its easternmost record comes from the Aegean Sea close to Limnos (emendation of SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1977a: Stat. DS-08/14). It is characterised by three rows of pedal shield scales and by the somewhat longitudinally rotated and asymmetrical midbody sclerites (up to 250 μm).

The known Iberian distribution refers to the southern Bay of Biscay, to

off central Portugal, to the Gulf of Cádiz and to off Morocco (off Ceuta to off Melilla; cf. SCHELTEMA AND IVANOV, 2000). There are four new records from off Barcelona: BIOM 1, BC 8; BIOM 3, BC 8 (4 mm long with up to 300 μm long scales); BIOM 4, BC 3; BIOM 4, BC 4.

Biogeographically, these findings border the occurrence of *P. alleni* from off Banyuls-sur-Mer/Côte Vermeille (Mediterranean coast of France: SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1977b; SCHELTEMA AND IVANOV, 2000).

Additional species

The presence of other Caudofoveata species from off Barcelona has already been communicated (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1997). There are additional records of *Falcidens*

gutturosus (Kowalevsky, 1901) from BIOM 2, BC 11 and BIOM 3, BC 3, as well as of *Falcidens aequabilis* Salvini-Plawen, 1972, from BIOM 3, BC 3 and BIOM 4, BC 4.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is very grateful to Mag. Emanuel Redl (Vienna) for assistance in preparing the photo-

graphs and to Dr. Michael Stachowitsch (Vienna) for polishing the English text.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- IVANOV D.L. AND SCHELTEMA A.H. 2001. Distribution of known caudofoveate species (Mollusca, Aplacophora) around Iceland. *Ruthenica* 11: 1-6.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1968. Über Lebendbeobachtungen an Caudofoveata (Mollusca, Aculifera), nebst Bemerkungen zum System der Klasse. *Sarsia* 31: 105-126.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1977a. Caudofoveata (Mollusca) des Forschungsprojektes Polymède. *Bulletin du Museum national d'Histoire naturelle*, 3^e sér. (447), Zoologie 310: 413-421.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1977b. Caudofoveata (Mollusca), Priapulida und Apode Holothurien (*Labidoplax*, *Myriotrochus*) bei Banyuls und im Mittelmeer allgemein. *Vie et Milieu*, 27 (A/1): 55-81.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1996. *Falcidens vasconensis* spec. nov. (Mollusca, Caudofoveata) du plateau continental du Golfe de Gascogne. *Bulletin de la Société Zoologique de France*, 121: 339-345.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1997. Fragmented knowledge on West-European and Iberian Caudofoveata and Solenogastres. *Iberus*, 15: 35-50.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 1999. Caudofoveata (Mollusca) from off the northern coast of the Iberian Peninsula. *Iberus*, 17 (2): 77-84.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 2003. On the phylogenetic significance of the aplacophoran Mollusca. *Iberus* 21 (1): 67-97.
- SALVINI-PLAWEN L.V. 2006. The significance of the Placophora for molluscan Phylogeny. *Venus* 65: 1-17.
- SCHELTEMA A.H. AND IVANOV D.L. 2000. Prochaetodermatidae of the eastern Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea (Mollusca: Aplacophora). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 66: 313-362.
- SCHELTEMA A.H. AND IVANOV D.L. 2001. Eastern Atlantic Prochaetodermatidae revisited: the nonsynonymy of *Prochaetoderma boucheti* Scheltema and Ivanov (Aplacophora). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 67: 396-398.